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Statins are highly effective against colo-rectal cancer

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Processes in nature, even pathological ones, are many times cholesterol dependent too. The discovery and the development of HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors (statins) could turn out to be more and more one of the finest hours of scientific research.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The relationship between statins and colo-rectal cancer has been re-investigated while using some new statistical methods.

RESULTS:

A long term use of statins is highly effective against colo-rectal cancer.

CONCLUSION:

Statins are very effective in protecting people against colo-rectal cancer.

Keywords:

Statins; Colo-rectal cancer; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Historically, François Poulletier de la Salle (1719–1788), a French doctor and chemist, identified solid cholesterol in gallstones in 1769.¹ · ² Some years later, in 1815, the French chemist Michel Eugène Chevreul (1786–1889) coined the notion cholesterine (solid bile; in Greek: chole for bile and stereos for solid).³ The Austrian botanist Friedrich Reinitzer was successful in 1888 to establish the molecular formula of cholesterol accurately.⁴ Heinrich Otto Wieland (1877–1957) and Adolf Otto Reinhold Windaus deciphered the structure of cholesterol in detail.⁵ · ⁶ Windaus himself reported in 1910 that atherosclerotic⁷ · ⁸ plaques from aortas of human subjects contained over 20-fold higher concentrations of cholesterol than did normal aortas.⁹ Nikolai N. Anichkov (1885–1964) fed pure cholesterol to rabbits and demonstrated experimentally the role of cholesterol in the development of atherosclerosis.¹⁰ · ¹¹ In the further of research, Goldstein and Brown formally demonstrated the existence of the postulated LDL receptor in 1974.¹² In point of fact, it was possible to discover that cholesterol is essential for the functioning of many human organs, but there might also be a dark side too. The Framingham Heart Study carried out by the National Heart Institute in Framingham claimed to have provided some, even if arguable, evidence that higher blood cholesterol levels are more likely to be related with myocardial infarction.¹³ · ¹⁴ The search for cholesterol-lowering drugs as one possible source of help against myocardial infarction became more and more urgent. Finally, in 1976, a young Japanese researcher, Akira Endo, working at Sankyo Pharmaceuticals in Tokyo¹⁵ discovered the first statin, named compactin, as a product of the fungus **Penicillium citrinum** which was able to inhibit the activity of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase. Akira Endo's extraordinarily brilliant assumption of far-reaching historical dimensions was that some organisms might produce HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors as a defense mechanism against infection agents which

¹Endo A. A historical perspective on the discovery of statins. *Proc Jpn Acad Ser B Phys Biol Sci.* 2010;86(5):484-93. doi: 10.2183/pjab.86.484. PMID: 20467214; PMCID: PMC3108295.

²Kuijpers, P. M. J. C. (2021). History in medicine: The story of cholesterol, lipids and cardiology. *J. Cradiol. Pract*, 19, 1-5.

³Chevreul, M. E. (1824). Note sur la presence de la cholesterine dans la bile de l'homme. *Mem Musee Hist nat Paris*, 11, 239-240.

⁴Reinitzer, F. Beiträge zur Kenntniss des Cholesterins. *Monatshefte für Chemie* 9, 421–441 (1888). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01516710>

⁵The Nobel Prize in Chemistry 1927. [NobelPrize.org](https://www.nobelprize.org).

⁶The Nobel Prize in Chemistry 1928. [NobelPrize.org](https://www.nobelprize.org).

⁷Marchand F. Ueber Atherosclerosis. *Verhandlungen der Kongresse fuer Innere Medizin*. 21 Kongresse, 1904.

⁸Ignatowski AI. Ueber die Wirkung der tierschen Einweisse auf der Aorta. *Virchow's Arch Pathol Anat* 1909;198:248.

⁹Windaus A. Ueber der Gehalt normaler und atheromatöser Aorten an Cholesterol und Cholesterinester. *Zeitschrift Physiol Chemie* 1910;67:174.

¹⁰Anitschkow N, Chalatow S. Ueber experimentelle Cholesterinsteatose und ihre Bedeutung fuer die Entstehung einiger pathologischer Prozesse. *Zentrbl Allg Pathol Pathol Anat* 1913;24:1–9.

¹¹Konstantinov IE, Mejevoi N, Anichkov NM, Nikolai N. Anichkov and his theory of atherosclerosis. *Tex Heart Inst J.* 2006;33(4):417-23. PMID: 17215962; PMCID: PMC1764970.

¹²Goldstein JL, Brown MS. Binding and degradation of low density lipoproteins by cultured human fibroblasts. Comparison of cells from a normal subject and from a patient with homozygous familial hypercholesterolemia. *J Biol Chem.* 1974 Aug 25;249(16):5153-62. PMID: 4368448.

¹³KANNEL WB, DAWBER TR, KAGAN A, REVOTSKIE N, STOKES J 3rd. Factors of risk in the development of coronary heart disease—six year follow-up experience. The Framingham Study. *Ann Intern Med.* 1961 Jul;55:33-50. doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-55-1-33. PMID: 13751193.

¹⁴Wilson PW, Garrison RJ, Castelli WP, Feinleib M, McNamara PM, Kannel WB. Prevalence of coronary heart disease in the Framingham Offspring Study: role of lipoprotein cholesterols. *Am J Cardiol.* 1980 Oct;46(4):649-54. doi: 10.1016/0002-9149(80)90516-0. PMID: 7416024.

¹⁵Lyons KS, Harbinson M. Statins: in the beginning. *J R Coll Physicians Edinb.* 2009 Dec;39(4):362-4. doi: 10.4997/jr-cpe.2009.425. PMID: 20509462

themselves require cholesterol or other steroids for their survival.¹⁶ After a lot of experiments over a two-year period, the research group working at Sankyo Pharmaceuticals in Tokyo isolated a molecule from cultures of *Penicillium citrinum* that appeared to be effective, ML236-B.8¹⁷ ·¹⁸ Meanwhile, various semi-synthetic statins like simvastatin (Zocor, Merck, 1991) and pravastatin (Pravachol, BMS, 1991) and synthetic statins like fluvastatin (Lescol, Sandoz, 1994), atorvastatin (Lipitor, Parke-Davis, 1996), rosuvastatin (Crestor, AstraZeneca, 2003) and other were introduced to the market. In other words, Hydroxymethylglutaryl-coenzyme A (HMG CoA) reductase inhibitors (statins) are one of the most widely prescribed medications worldwide for lowering the blood cholesterol level. 3-Hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase inhibitors, commonly known as statins, are very effective lipid-lowering agents. However, does this group of drugs exhibit other, antiviral¹⁹ ·²⁰ and even antimicrobial effects? Studies showed that statins exhibit indeed antimicrobial effects against various microorganisms. Additionally, statins possess antiviral properties against human cytomegalovirus et cetera, have antifungal properties²¹ and are potentially effective against colo-rectal cancer (CRC) too. This issue has been the subject of a closer examination in this publication.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

¹⁶Endo A. The discovery and development of HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors. *J Lipid Res.* 1992 Nov;33(11):1569-82. PMID: 1464741.

¹⁷Endo A, Kuroda M, Tsujita Y. ML-236A, ML-236B, and ML-236C, new inhibitors of cholesterol synthesis produced by *Penicillium citrinum*. *J Antibiot (Tokyo)*. 1976 Dec;29(12):1346-8. doi: 10.7164/antibiotics.29.1346. PMID: 1010803.

¹⁸Endo A, Kuroda M, Tanzawa K. Competitive inhibition of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase by ML-236A and ML-236B fungal metabolites, having hypocholesterolemic activity. 1976. *Atheroscler Suppl.* 2004 Oct;5(3):39-42. doi: 10.1016/j.atherosclerosissup.2004.08.021. PMID: 15531273.

¹⁹Heaton NS, Randall G. Multifaceted roles for lipids in viral infection. *Trends Microbiol.* 2011 Jul;19(7):368-75. doi: 10.1016/j.tim.2011.03.007. Epub 2011 Apr 29. PMID: 21530270; PMCID: PMC3130080.

²⁰Rothwell C, Lebreton A, Young Ng C, Lim JY, Liu W, Vasudevan S, Labow M, Gu F, Gaither LA. Cholesterol biosynthesis modulation regulates dengue viral replication. *Virology.* 2009 Jun 20;389(1-2):8-19. doi: 10.1016/j.virol.2009.03.025. Epub 2009 May 5. PMID: 19419745.

²¹Ting M, Whitaker EJ, Albandar JM. Systematic review of the in vitro effects of statins on oral and perioral microorganisms. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2016 Feb;124(1):4-10. doi: 10.1111/eos.12239. Epub 2015 Dec 30. PMID: 26718458.

2.2. The Study of Graaf et al., 2004, The Netherlands

Matthijs R Graaf et al. ²² investigated the role for 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme A reductase inhibitors (statins) in the treatment of colon cancer. The Graaf et al. observational study suggests that statins have a protective effect against cancer. Graaf et al. reported, that 33/3129 of cases which used statins for more than 4 years developed colon cancer while 276 / 16976 of controls developed colon cancer. The probability of the exclusion relationship between statins and colorectal cancer is $p(\text{EXCL}) = 1 - (33 / (3129 + 16976)) = 0.9983586173$ (see table 1).

Table 1. Statin use over 4 years and more and colorectal cancer (Study of Graaf et al., 2004).

		Colorectal cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin > 4 years	YES	33	276	309
	NO	3096	16700	19796
		3129	16976	20105

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,01683145$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00825272
p (EXCL) = 0,99835862
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,89320388
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,98945350

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00825272
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_t) = 3,52427184
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_t) = 0,34803452
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,00164004

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (33 / 309) \times 100 = 10,68 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (276 / 309) \times 100 = 89,32 \%$
 $(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (3096 / 19796) \times 100 = 15,64 \%$
 $(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (16700 / 19796) \times 100 = 84,36 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (33 / 3129) \times 100 = 1,05 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (3096 / 3129) \times 100 = 98,95 \%$
 $(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (276 / 16976) \times 100 = 1,63 \%$
 $(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (16700 / 16976) \times 100 = 98,37 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (309 / 20105) \times 100 = 1,54 \%$
 $(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (19796 / 20105) \times 100 = 98,46 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (3129 / 20105) \times 100 = 15,56 \%$
 $(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (16976 / 20105) \times 100 = 84,44 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,68286044
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,64868620

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,64494158
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,31379485

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,82899776
p(IOI) = 0,14026362

A long year use of statins over 4 years or more excludes colorectal cancer ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0.99835862$; P Value (EXCL) = 0.00164004) even if the prevalence of colorectal cancer ($(B/N) \times 100 = (3129 / 20105) \times 100 = 15.56 \%$) in the population as proposed by Graaf et al. is too high.

²²Graaf MR, Beiderbeck AB, Egberts AC, Richel DJ, Guchelaar HJ. The risk of cancer in users of statins. *J Clin Oncol.* 2004 Jun 15;22(12):2388-94. doi: 10.1200/JCO.2004.02.027. PMID: 15197200.

2.3. *The MECC Study, 2005, Israel*

Statins are able to inhibit the growth of colon-cancer cell lines²³,²⁴,²⁵ and potentially reduce the risk of colo-rectal cancer. The Molecular Epidemiology of Colo-rectal Cancer (MECC) population-based case-control study used a structured interview to determine the use of statins in Israel of more than 5 years was associated with a reduction in risk of colo-rectal cancer. Simvastatin and pravastatin were the two most commonly used statins in this study group.²⁶

²³Al-Haidari AA, Syk I, Thorlacius H. HMG-CoA reductase regulates CCL17-induced colon cancer cell migration via geranylgeranylation and RhoA activation. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 2014 Mar 28;446(1):68-72. doi: 10.1016/j.bbrc.2014.02.078. Epub 2014 Feb 25. PMID: 24582560.

²⁴Zheng XF, Liu KX, Wang XM, Zhang R, Li X. MicroRNA-192 acts as a tumor suppressor in colon cancer and simvastatin activates miR-192 to inhibit cancer cell growth. *Mol Med Rep*. 2019 Mar;19(3):1753-1760. doi: 10.3892/mmr.2019.9808. Epub 2019 Jan 2. PMID: 30628692.

²⁵Cai S, Gao Z. Atorvastatin inhibits proliferation and promotes apoptosis of colon cancer cells via COX-2/PGE2/ β -Catenin Pathway. *J BUON*. 2021 Jul-Aug;26(4):1219-1225. PMID: 34564973.

²⁶Poynter JN, Gruber SB, Higgins PD, Almog R, Bonner JD, Rennert HS, Low M, Greenson JK, Rennert G. Statins and the risk of colo-rectal cancer. *N Engl J Med*. 2005 May 26;352(21):2184-92. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa043792. PMID: 15917383.

Table 2. Statin therapy over 5 years or more and colorectal cancer (Study of Poynter et al.,2005).

		Colo-rectal cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy > 5 years	YES	120	234	354
	NO	1833	1781	3614
		1953	2015	3968

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,09590957$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,96975806
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,66101695
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,93855607

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 40,67796610
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 7,37327189
P Value (EXCL) = 0,02978922

PROPORTIONS.

(a/A) × 100 = (120 / 354) × 100 = 33,90 %
(b/A) × 100 = (234 / 354) × 100 = 66,10 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (1833 / 3614) × 100 = 50,72 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (1781 / 3614) × 100 = 49,28 %
(a/B) × 100 = (120 / 1953) × 100 = 6,14 %
(c/B) × 100 = (1833 / 1953) × 100 = 93,86 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (234 / 2015) × 100 = 11,61 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (1781 / 2015) × 100 = 88,39 %
(A/N) × 100 = (354 / 3968) × 100 = 8,92 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (3614 / 3968) × 100 = 91,08 %
(B/N) × 100 = (1953 / 3968) × 100 = 49,22 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (2015 / 3968) × 100 = 50,78 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 0,66834956
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,52910053

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,49827241
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,31127253

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,41859879
p(IOI)= 0,40297379

The prevalence of colo-rectal cancer in the population according to Poynter et al. is about (B/N) × 100 = (1953 / 3968) × 100 = 49.22 % which is extremely biased. Such a value is far from being true or acceptable. The study design with p(IOI)= 0.40297379 is very unfair. All together, the data of Poynter et al. are only of very restricted value.

2.3.1. Statin therapy over 5 years and colon cancer (Poynter et al., 2005)

Table 3. Statin therapy over 5 years and more and colon cancer (Study of Poynter et al., 2005).

		Colon cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy > 5 years	YES	11	43	54
	NO	78	737	815
		89	780	869

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.Causal relationship $k = 0,08599037$

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99421158

p (EXCL) = 0,98734177**p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,79629630****p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,87640449****P VALUES.**

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,99421158

 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_t) = 2,24074074 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_t) = 1,35955056

P Value (EXCL) = 0,01257845

PROPORTIONS. $(a/A) \times 100 = (11 / 54) \times 100 = 20,37 \%$ $(b/A) \times 100 = (43 / 54) \times 100 = 79,63 \%$ $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (78 / 815) \times 100 = 9,57 \%$ $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (737 / 815) \times 100 = 90,43 \%$ $(a/B) \times 100 = (11 / 89) \times 100 = 12,36 \%$ $(c/B) \times 100 = (78 / 89) \times 100 = 87,64 \%$ $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (43 / 780) \times 100 = 5,51 \%$ $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (737 / 780) \times 100 = 94,49 \%$ $(A/N) \times 100 = (54 / 869) \times 100 = 6,21 \%$ $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (815 / 869) \times 100 = 93,79 \%$ $(B/N) \times 100 = (89 / 869) \times 100 = 10,24 \%$ $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (780 / 869) \times 100 = 89,76 \%$ **ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.****RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 2,12844255

RR (sufficient condition) = 2,24196499

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 2,41711389

Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,98897212

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,83544304

p(IOI)= 0,04027618

2.3.2. Statin therapy over 5 years and more and rectal cancer (Poynter et al., 2005)

Table 4. Statin therapy > 5 years and rectal cancer (Study of Poynter et al., 2005).

		Rectal cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy > 5 years	YES	1	12	13
	NO	32	299	331
		33	311	344

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,01279075$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,64026841
p (EXCL) = 0,99709302
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,92307692
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,96969697

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,64026841
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_t) = 0,07692308
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_t) = 0,03030303
P Value (EXCL) = 0,00290276

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (1 / 13) \times 100 = 7,69 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (12 / 13) \times 100 = 92,31 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (32 / 331) \times 100 = 9,67 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (299 / 331) \times 100 = 90,33 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (1 / 33) \times 100 = 3,03 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (32 / 33) \times 100 = 96,97 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (12 / 311) \times 100 = 3,86 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (299 / 311) \times 100 = 96,14 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (13 / 344) \times 100 = 3,78 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (331 / 344) \times 100 = 96,22 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (33 / 344) \times 100 = 9,59 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (311 / 344) \times 100 = 90,41 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 0,79567308
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,78535354

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,77864583
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,19813520

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,86627907
p(IOI) = 0,05813953

The prevalence of rectal cancer in the population according to Poynter et al. is about $(B/N) \times 100 = (33 / 344) \times 100 = 9.59 \%$ which is obviously high. Even the data of this subgroup of Poynter et al. are only of very restricted value.

2.3.3. Statin therapy and inflammatory bowel disease (Poynter et al., 2005)

Poynter et al. examined the relationship between statin use and inflammatory bowel disease and we observed a protective effect of statins. The anti-inflammatory properties of statins have been verified by another study, too.

Table 5. Statin therapy > 5 years and inflammatory bowel disease (Study of Poynter et al. , 2005).

		Inflammatory bowel disease		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy > 5 years	YES	1	5	6
	NO	38	11	49
		39	16	55

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,41791415$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00615254
p (EXCL) = 0,98181818
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,83333333
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,97435897

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00615254
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_t) = 0,16666667
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_t) = 0,02564103
P Value (EXCL) = 0,01801753

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (1 / 6) \times 100 = 16,67 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (5 / 6) \times 100 = 83,33 \%$
 $(c / \text{not } A) \times 100 = (38 / 49) \times 100 = 77,55 \%$
 $(d / \text{not } A) \times 100 = (11 / 49) \times 100 = 22,45 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (1 / 39) \times 100 = 2,56 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (38 / 39) \times 100 = 97,44 \%$
 $(b / \text{not } B) \times 100 = (5 / 16) \times 100 = 31,25 \%$
 $(d / \text{not } B) \times 100 = (11 / 16) \times 100 = 68,75 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (6 / 55) \times 100 = 10,91 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (49 / 55) \times 100 = 89,09 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (39 / 55) \times 100 = 70,91 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (16 / 55) \times 100 = 29,09 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,21491228
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,08205128

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,05789474
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,76495726

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,18181818
p(IOI)= 0,60000000

The prevalence an inflammatory bovel disease in the population according to Poynter et al. is about $(B/N) \times 100 = (39 / 55) \times 100 = 70,91 \%$ which is to high and unacceptable in this way. The placebo group has been to small. The relationship between statin therapy for 5 years or more and inflammatory bovel disease will be better and stronger than suggested by the study of Poynter et al.

2.4. The Study Jacobs et al., 2006, USA

Jacobs et al. ²⁷ examined the relationship between the long-duration use of 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase inhibitors for 5 years or more, cholesterol-lowering drugs, and colo-rectal cancer among 132,136 men and women in the so called Cancer Prevention Study II Nutrition Cohort. During follow-up Jacobs et al. identified 815 incident cases of colo-rectal cancer among these participants. Based on the results of the statistical analysis, Jacobs et al. concluded that statins used for 5 years or more do not reduce the risk of colo-rectal cancer.

Table 6. Statin therapy over 5 years or more and colo-rectal cancer (Study of Jacobs et al., 2006).

		Colo-rectal cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statin therapy > 5 years	YES	72	23288	23360
	NO	671	102683	103354
		743	125971	126714

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,01731937$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
p (EXCL) = 0,99943179
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,99691781
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,90309556

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 0,22191781
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 6,97711978
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,00056805

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (72 / 23360) \times 100 = 0,31 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (23288 / 23360) \times 100 = 99,69 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (671 / 103354) \times 100 = 0,65 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (102683 / 103354) \times 100 = 99,35 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (72 / 743) \times 100 = 9,69 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (671 / 743) \times 100 = 90,31 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (23288 / 125971) \times 100 = 18,49 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (102683 / 125971) \times 100 = 81,51 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (23360 / 126714) \times 100 = 18,44 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (103354 / 126714) \times 100 = 81,56 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (743 / 126714) \times 100 = 0,59 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (125971 / 126714) \times 100 = 99,41 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,47474940
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,52418196

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,47312547
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,47435148

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,80978424
p(IOI) = 0,17848856

²⁷Jacobs EJ, Rodriguez C, Brady KA, Connell CJ, Thun MJ, Calle EE. Cholesterol-lowering drugs and colo-rectal cancer incidence in a large United States cohort. J Natl Cancer Inst. 2006 Jan 4;98(1):69-72. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djj006. PMID: 16391373.

Colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer diagnosed in the United States. The observed rate of new cases of colorectal cancer, also referred to as incidence rate, in the United States for 2019 has been reported as 34.10 per 100000 men and women per year ²⁸ or in other words 0.0341 %. The United States had an official estimated resident population of, 327964770 on May 1, 2019, according to the U.S. Census Bureau. ²⁹ According to the U. S. National Cancer Institute, in 2019, about 1369005 people suffered from colorectal cancer in the United States. **The 2019 prevalence of colorectal cancer in U.S. has been about: US prevalence (colo-rectal cancer) = $B/N \times 100 = (1369005/327964770) \times 100 = 0.4174244081\%$** ³⁰ **The prevalence of colorectal cancer reported by Jacobs et al. has been $(B/N) \times 100 = (743 / 126714) \times 100 = 0.59\%$ and is slightly too big but not heavily biased.** The data of Jacobs et al. are of use, while the study design with $p(\text{IOI}) = 0.17848856$ has been unfair and could have been better. The control group of the study of Jacobs et al. has been too small, with the consequence that the relationship between the use of statins and the exclusion of colorectal cancer as found by Jacobs et al. is much stronger and much better than already reported.

²⁸National Cancer Institute.Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results Program. Cancer Stat Facts: Colorectal Cancer

²⁹U.S. Census Bureau. 4600 Silver Hill Road. Washington, DC 20233. Monthly Population Estimates for the United States: April 1, 2010 to December 1, 2020 (NA-EST2019-01).

³⁰U.S. Department of Health and Human Services - National Institutes of Health - National Cancer Institute - Cancer Stat Facts: colo-rectal Cancer

2.5. The Study of Hoffmeister et al., 2007, Germany

Hoffmeister et al. ³¹ examined the protective effects of statins on 540 cases with histologically confirmed incident colorectal cancer and 614 control subjects in a population-based case-control study in Germany. Hoffmeister reported that 14 / 440 cases with continuous use of statins over 5 years and more developed colorectal cancer while 21 / 483 controls developed colorectal cancer. The probability of the exclusion relationship between statins and colorectal cancer is $p(\text{EXCL}) = 1 - (14 / (440 + 483)) = 0.9848320693$ (see table 7) and to some extent impressive.

Table 7. Use of statins > 5 years and Colorectal cancer (Study of Hoffmeister et al., 2007), Germany.

		Colorectal cancer		
		YES	NO	
Statins > 5 years	YES	14	21	35
	NO	426	462	888
		440	483	923

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,03049024$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,22605156
 $p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,98483207$
 $p(\text{EXCL}) \text{ approx.} = 1 - (a/A) > 0,60000000$
 $p(\text{EXCL}) \text{ approx.} = 1 - (a/B) > 0,96818182$

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,22605156
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{EXCL} - A_i) = 5,60000000$
 $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{EXCL} - B_i) = 0,44545455$
P Value (EXCL) = 0,01505348

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (14 / 35) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (21 / 35) \times 100 = 60,00 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (426 / 888) \times 100 = 47,97 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (462 / 888) \times 100 = 52,03 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (14 / 440) \times 100 = 3,18 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (426 / 440) \times 100 = 96,82 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (21 / 483) \times 100 = 4,35 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (462 / 483) \times 100 = 95,65 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (35 / 923) \times 100 = 3,79 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (888 / 923) \times 100 = 96,21 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (440 / 923) \times 100 = 47,67 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (483 / 923) \times 100 = 52,33 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,83380282
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,73181818

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,72300469
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,16090909

STUDY DESIGN.

$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,48537378$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,43878657$

³¹Hoffmeister M, Chang-Claude J, Brenner H. Individual and joint use of statins and low-dose aspirin and risk of colorectal cancer: a population-based case-control study. *Int J Cancer*. 2007 Sep 15;121(6):1325-30. doi: 10.1002/ijc.22796. PMID: 17487832.

2.6. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*³² too.

2.6.1. Exclusion relationship

The probability of the exclusion relationship $p(\text{EXCL})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B)$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an exclusion relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, left-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided left-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a positive causal relationship would contradict an exclusion relationship and vice versa.

2.6.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 8. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	d
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher,

³²Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.6.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution³³. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

³³Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

2.6.4. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (6)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.6.5. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (7)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\bar{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\bar{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see Barukčić, 2019, p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (9)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 9 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (10)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots \text{ vs. } H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (11)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (12)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (13)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see Barukčić, 2019, p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the population distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the the probability of a population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

2.6.6. Bonferroni correction

Multiple testing at a certain level of significance α might amplify the probability of false-positive findings. In other words, the more inferences are made (on a certain data body i. e. subgroup analyses et cetera), the more likely erroneous inferences might realise. At the end, several independent or dependent statistical tests performed simultaneously (on the same data body) can induce the so called family-wise error rate (FWER) or multiple testing problem. The family-wise error rate or multiple testing problem (see [Tukey, 1994](#)) is ascribed to John Wilder Tukey (1915 – 2000), an American mathematician and statistician. The probability that at least one null hypothesis out of k null hypotheses tested is falsely rejected is no longer equal to the overall significance level α but equal to

$$\alpha_{\text{FWER}} = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k \quad (15)$$

As a consequence, a higher significance threshold for an individual hypothesis, denoted as α_i , is demanded. Various statistical techniques have been developed to address this problem. The Bonferroni multiple-comparison correction (see [Bonferroni, 1936](#); [Dunn, 1961](#)) is one of the solutions proposed to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

Example

An investigation is testing $m = 4$ hypotheses with a desired $\alpha = 0.05$. Under these circumstances, the Bonferroni correction might be of appropriate use. Each individual hypothesis should be tested at a single level of significance, α_i given as,

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\alpha}{m} = \frac{0,05}{4} = 0.0125 \quad (16)$$

where m is the total number of hypotheses tested and α is the overall significance level. By requiring a stricter significance threshold, **an inflation of false positive results** can be prevented. In the context of further scientific development, there have been several trials to improve the Bonferroni method. One of these attempts is the so-called Rom's Method, published 1990 by Rom (see [Rom, 1990](#)) himself.

3. Results

3.1. Statins are highly effective against colo-rectal cancer

Theorem 1 (Statins are highly effective against colo-rectal cancer).

H0: (null hypothesis)

A long-term use of statins is highly effective against colo-rectal cancer.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

A long-term use of statins is not highly effective against colo-rectal cancer.

Proof by the study of Jacobs et al. The data of the study of Jacobs et al. ³⁴ have been re-analysed (see table 6). The study design of this study is to some extent appropriate enough for our purposes ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0.17848856$). Formally, the data are not self-contradictory (Causal relationship $k < 0$). The proof of an exclusion relationship is possible. The exclusion relationship between a long term use of statins and colo-rectal cancer is highly significant ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0.99943179$; P Value (EXCL) = 0.00056805) while the causal relationship k itself is negative and highly significant too (Causal relationship $k = -0,01731937$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0.00000000). The conclusion is inescapable. A long term use of statins excludes colo-rectal cancer and is an effective anti-dot against colo-rectal cancer ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0.99943179$; P Value (EXCL) = 0.00056805).

□

³⁴Jacobs EJ, Rodriguez C, Brady KA, Connell CJ, Thun MJ, Calle EE. Cholesterol-lowering drugs and colo-rectal cancer incidence in a large United States cohort. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2006 Jan 4;98(1):69-72. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djj006. PMID: 16391373.

4. Discussion

It is highly commendable that colo-rectal cancer (CRC) screening has reduced the incidence and the mortality from CRC. Nonetheless, chemoprevention strategies have the potential to further reduce CRC incidence and mortality. Does the use of statins possess any potential benefits in this context? Poynter et al. (Israel, 2005)³⁵ used a structured interview to determine whether the use of statins has any effect on colo-rectal cancer. The data provided are to some extent self-contradictory (see table 2, 3, 4) and of little use. In spite of all self-made hurdles Poynter et al. were able to provide slight but self-contradictory evidence that statin use excludes colo-rectal cancer (see table 2). Poynter et al. have also been able to provide some substantiated evidence of the relationship between inflammatory bowel disease and statin use (see 5). Unfortunately, the study design of the sub-group analysed has not been very convincing. Nevertheless, Poynter et al. could demonstrate that the use of statins excludes inflammatory bowel disease (see 5) and may be a potent treatment for Crohn's disease. These findings are consistent with the results of other studies. Kang et al. (Division of Pulmonology, Department of Internal Medicine, Severance Hospital, Yonsei University College of Medicine, Seoul, Republic of Korea) were able to provide evidence that the use of statins excludes the development of tuberculosis with a probability of $p(\text{EXCL}) = (1 - (504 / (840899))) = 0.99940064$ (P Value = 0.0005991).³⁶ ³⁷ An infection by mycobacterium avium subspecies paratuberculosis (MAP) is often transmitted by birds, by livestock herds and other sources. Unfortunately, Mycobacteria are intracellular pathogens which are able to invade and survive within host macrophages, thereby creating a major economic and health threat in most areas of the world.³⁸ Especially, Mycobacterium avium subspecies paratuberculosis is closely related to pathogenic mycobacteria such as M. tuberculosis and is the cause of Johne's disease and of Morbus Crohn.³⁹ Cholesterol is an essential component of microorganisms, cells⁴⁰, cell membranes et cetera and contributes to the intracellular survival⁴¹ of microorganisms and is equally a key requirement for the entry of mycobacteria into macrophages⁴² and their survival.⁴³ MAP itself is able to manipulate and use host lipid metabolism⁴⁴ during early infection. Johansen et al. provided evidence of increases in the intracellular cholesterol levels of MAP-infected macrophages during early

³⁵Poynter JN, Gruber SB, Higgins PD, Almog R, Bonner JD, Rennert HS, Low M, Greenson JK, Rennert G. Statins and the risk of colo-rectal cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2005 May 26;352(21):2184-92. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa043792. PMID: 15917383.

³⁶Kang YA, Choi NK, Seong JM, Heo EY, Koo BK, Hwang SS, Park BJ, Yim JJ, Lee CH. The effects of statin use on the development of tuberculosis among patients with diabetes mellitus. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2014 Jun;18(6):717-24. doi: 10.5588/ijtld.13.0854. Erratum in: *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2015 May;19(5):622. PMID: 24903944.

³⁷Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Cytomegalovirus and lung cancer - a causal relationship?. *Causation*, 18(11), 5–38. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7722130>, p. 27

³⁸Gatfield J, Pieters J. Essential role for cholesterol in entry of mycobacteria into macrophages. *Science.* 2000 Jun 2;288(5471):1647-50. doi: 10.1126/science.288.5471.1647. PMID: 10834844.

³⁹Barukčić, I. (2018). Mycobacterium avium subspecies paratuberculosis. The Cause of Crohn's Disease. *Modern Health Science*, 1(1), pp. 19-34.

⁴⁰Chang KO. Role of cholesterol pathways in norovirus replication. *J Virol.* 2009;83(17):8587–95. doi: 10.1128/JVI.00005-09.

⁴¹de Chastellier C, Thilo L. Cholesterol depletion in Mycobacterium avium-infected macrophages overcomes the block in phagosome maturation and leads to the reversible sequestration of viable mycobacteria in phagolysosome-derived autophagic vacuoles. *Cell Microbiol.* 2006 Feb;8(2):242-56. doi: 10.1111/j.1462-5822.2005.00617.x. PMID: 16441435.

⁴²Gatfield J, Pieters J. Essential role for cholesterol in entry of mycobacteria into macrophages. *Science.* 2000 Jun 2;288(5471):1647-50. doi: 10.1126/science.288.5471.1647. PMID: 10834844.

⁴³Pandey AK, Sassetti CM. Mycobacterial persistence requires the utilization of host cholesterol. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA.* 2008;105(11):4376–80. doi: 10.1073/pnas.0711159105.

⁴⁴Koo MS, Subbian S, Kaplan G. Strain specific transcriptional response in Mycobacterium tuberculosis infected macrophages. *Cell Commun Signal.* 2012 Jan 26;10(1):2. doi: 10.1186/1478-811X-10-2. PMID: 22280836; PMCID: PMC3317440.

MAP infection. ⁴⁵ The prevalence rate of *Mycobacterium avium* subspecies *paratuberculosis* is exceeding 50% in dairy herds. It is therefore not surprising that the economic burden of *Mycobacterium avium* subspecies *paratuberculosis* relates to decreased milk production, to the costs of disease prevention, treatment et cetera while having a serious economic and health impact on dairy producers, processors, consumers, and stakeholders of the dairy industry. Is the supplemental feeding of livestock herds with a suitable statin a cost-effective and side-effect-free alternative to get the dramatic MAP problem under control? This fundamental question may be answered in detail at another occasion. However, regardless of this issue, the important question arises whether these trains of thought and recognised relationships are valid for the growth of cancer cells too? ⁴⁶, ⁴⁷, ⁴⁸, ⁴⁹ Colo-rectal cancer is caused by *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, which itself is potentially cholesterol dependent too. ⁵⁰ Graaf et al. ⁵¹ (see table 1) provided convincing evidence that a year-long statin use excludes colorectal cancer even if the prevalence of colorectal cancer with $((B/N) \times 100 = (3129 / 20105) \times 100 = 15.56 \%)$ in the population as estimated by Graaf et al. is too high. As a consequence, the relationship between a year-long statin use and colorectal cancer is much stronger than Graaf et al. suggested. Jacobs et al. ⁵² examined the relationship between the long-duration use of statins for 5 years or more and colo-rectal cancer (see table 6). The study design with $p(\text{IOI}) = 0.17848856$ was acceptable while the prevalence of colorectal cancer within the population investigated has been very impressive $((B/N) \times 100 = (743 / 126714) \times 100 = 0.59 \%)$, sample size $N = 126714$). Taking into account all conceivable advantages and disadvantages, the data published by Jacobs et al. are of good quality and can accordingly be considered in more detail. Unfortunately, Jacobs et al. used very inappropriate statistical methods and reached the following erroneous conclusion. **“Our results do not support the hypothesis that statin use strongly reduces risk of colorectal cancer.”**⁵³ We have high quality data based justified reason to reject such a conclusion in the strongest possible manner. The exclusion relationship between the long term use of statins and colo-rectal cancer is highly significant ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,99943179$; P Value (EXCL) = 0,00056805) while the cause-effect relationship is negative and highly significant too (Causal relationship $k = -0,01731937$; P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000). The efficacy of a long-term therapy with statins against colo-rectal cancer ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0,99943179$; P Value (EXCL) = 0,00056805) is comparable to the efficacy of a vaccination with Pfizer/Biontech’s mRNA

⁴⁵Johansen MD, de Silva K, Plain KM, Whittington RJ, Purdie AC. *Mycobacterium avium* subspecies *paratuberculosis* is able to manipulate host lipid metabolism and accumulate cholesterol within macrophages. *Microb Pathog.* 2019 May;130:44-53. doi: 10.1016/j.micpath.2019.02.031. Epub 2019 Mar 1. PMID: 30831227.

⁴⁶Campbell MJ, Esserman LJ, Zhou Y, Shoemaker M, Lobo M, Borman E, Baehner F, Kumar AS, Adduci K, Marx C, Petricoin EF, Liotta LA, Winters M, Benz S, Benz CC. Breast cancer growth prevention by statins. *Cancer Res.* 2006 Sep 1;66(17):8707-14. doi: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-05-4061. PMID: 16951186.

⁴⁷Beckwitt CH, Shiraha K, Wells A. Lipophilic statins limit cancer cell growth and survival, via involvement of Akt signaling. *PLoS One.* 2018 May 15;13(5):e0197422. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0197422. PMID: 29763460; PMCID: PMC5953490.

⁴⁸Tilija Pun N, Jeong CH. Statin as a Potential Chemotherapeutic Agent: Current Updates as a Monotherapy, Combination Therapy, and Treatment for Anti-Cancer Drug Resistance. *Pharmaceuticals (Basel).* 2021 May 16;14(5):470. doi: 10.3390/ph14050470. PMID: 34065757; PMCID: PMC8156779.

⁴⁹Hoque A, Chen H, Xu XC. Statin induces apoptosis and cell growth arrest in prostate cancer cells. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2008 Jan;17(1):88-94. doi: 10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-07-0531. PMID: 18199714.

⁵⁰Barukčić, I. (2018). *Fusobacterium nucleatum—The Cause of Human Colorectal Cancer.* *Journal of Biosciences and Medicines*, 6(3), 31-69.

⁵¹Graaf MR, Beiderbeck AB, Egberts AC, Richel DJ, Guchelaar HJ. The risk of cancer in users of statins. *J Clin Oncol.* 2004 Jun 15;22(12):2388-94. doi: 10.1200/JCO.2004.02.027. PMID: 15197200.

⁵²Jacobs EJ, Rodriguez C, Brady KA, Connell CJ, Thun MJ, Calle EE. Cholesterol-lowering drugs and colo-rectal cancer incidence in a large United States cohort. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2006 Jan 4;98(1):69-72. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djj006. PMID: 16391373.

⁵³Jacobs EJ, Rodriguez C, Brady KA, Connell CJ, Thun MJ, Calle EE. Cholesterol-lowering drugs and colo-rectal cancer incidence in a large United States cohort. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2006 Jan 4;98(1):69-72. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djj006. PMID: 16391373.

vaccine against Covid 19 ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 1 - (8/43448) = 0,999815872$; P Value = 0,000184128).⁵⁴,⁵⁵ The prevalence of colorectal cancer in the population with $((B/N) \times 100 = (1953 / 3968) \times 100 = 49,22 \%)$ as reported by Poynter et al., 2005 is absolutely too high (see table 3). In reality, the prevalence of colorectal cancer in the population is much lower with the consequence, the relationship between a year-long use of statins and the protection against colorectal cancer is much stronger than found by the data of the Poynter et al. study. In other words, the data of the study of Poynter et al.⁵⁶ have been treated as biased and did not enter the final conclusion (see table 3) drawn. The prevalence of colorectal cancer in the population with $((B/N) \times 100 = (440 / 923) \times 100 = 47.67 \%)$ as reported by Hoffmeister et al.⁵⁷ is equally too high (see table 7). In reality, the prevalence of colorectal cancer in the population is much lower than claimed by Hoffmeister et al. with the consequence, the relationship between a year-long use of statins and the protection against colorectal cancer is much stronger than found by the data of the Hoffmeister et al. study. Therefore, the data of the study of Hoffmeister et al.⁵⁸ have been treated as being biased and have not been considered for the final conclusion (see table 7) drawn. Thus far, even if statins are not as effective as desired against acute myocardial infarction⁵⁹, especially the data of the study of Jacobs et al.⁶⁰ does not leave any further space for remaining doubts (see theorem 1).

5. Conclusion

Based on very hard, high-quality data we have no other choice but to arrive at the following and straightforward conclusion.

‘A long-term use of statins is a highly effective measure against colo-rectal cancer.’

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⁵⁴Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

⁵⁵Barukčić, Ilija. (2021). COVID-19 vaccines - a great leap forward?. *Causation*, 6(12), 5–53. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5779506>, p. 42.

⁵⁶Poynter JN, Gruber SB, Higgins PD, Almog R, Bonner JD, Rennert HS, Low M, Greenson JK, Rennert G. Statins and the risk of colo-rectal cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2005 May 26;352(21):2184-92. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa043792. PMID: 15917383.

⁵⁷Hoffmeister M, Chang-Claude J, Brenner H. Individual and joint use of statins and low-dose aspirin and risk of colorectal cancer: a population-based case-control study. *Int J Cancer.* 2007 Sep 15;121(6):1325-30. doi: 10.1002/ijc.22796. PMID: 17487832.

⁵⁸Hoffmeister M, Chang-Claude J, Brenner H. Individual and joint use of statins and low-dose aspirin and risk of colorectal cancer: a population-based case-control study. *Int J Cancer.* 2007 Sep 15;121(6):1325-30. doi: 10.1002/ijc.22796. PMID: 17487832.

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⁶⁰Jacobs EJ, Rodriguez C, Brady KA, Connell CJ, Thun MJ, Calle EE. Cholesterol-lowering drugs and colo-rectal cancer incidence in a large United States cohort. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2006 Jan 4;98(1):69-72. doi: 10.1093/jnci/djj006. PMID: 16391373.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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^l<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>